

ARCHIVES GATEWAY

Bespoke application

User: Queensland State Agencies

Purpose: Transfer of digital and physical records with metadata. Provide agency access to transferred records.

Benefits: Secure access per Agency. Permission levels to account for record sensitives. Can chat through transfers, loans and access.

The **Queensland State Archives (QSA)** connects Queenslanders with their past – the histories of families, local communities, and the state by looking after the largest documentary heritage collection in Queensland. We manage, preserve and provide public access to the collection for the use and benefit of present and future generations. By collaborating with Gaia, we have developed a full featured end-to-end digital preservation workflow for Queensland public authorities.

ARCHIVES SEARCH

Bespoke application

User: Public

Purpose: Provide access to open records and enable requests.

Benefits: Publication is controlled via ArchivesSpace. Users can download open digital records. Users can request restricted records with published metadata.

ARCHIVES SPACE

Open-source Archival Management System

User: QSA Archivists

Purpose: Point of truth for QSA for archival records, preservation, and use.

Benefits: Integrates seamlessly with other systems. Uses plugins to facilitate Australian Series System and other customisations.

Gaia Resources is a sustainable IT consultancy specialising in open-source software implemented on cloud infrastructure. Our team includes staff experienced in archives and collecting institutions. Together with QSA we developed a system that is best in class and that facilitates the complete digital workflow required by archives.

ARCHIVEMATICA

Open-source Digital Preservation System

User: Archivists

Purpose: Generate AIPs, provide access copies, run fixity across 2 storage systems.

Benefits: Archivists action from ArchivesSpace. Links to AIPs, DIPs, PREMIS events, reingest and reports are all in ArchivesSpace.

TOGETHER
IN
ARCHIVAL
DREAMS

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